

Densification characteristics of ZrO₂ doped pure Al₂O₃ ceramics synthesized through co-precipitation route

A. Chakraborty, B. K. Sanfui and T. K. Parya*

Department of Chemical Technology, Ceramic Engineering Division, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : mailme.tapan@gmail.com Fax : 91-33-23519755

Manuscript received online 26 June 2012, revised 17 July 2012, accepted 07 August 2012

Abstract : In this study, the co-precipitated hydroxides hydrogels of aluminium and zirconium containing very small proportion of ZrO₂ varying from 0–0.3% (w/w) only have been synthesized by wet chemical interaction of requisite quantity of 0.2 M solution of aluminium isopropoxide and zirconium oxychloride dissolved in 1 : 1 isopropanol-water mixture at pH value from 3.5–4.0 under reflux at 80 °C. The double hydroxides gel precursor of aluminium and zirconium are characterized by specific surface area, DTA, FTIR studies. Zirconia toughened sintered pure alumina body with significant improvement of thermo mechanical properties and fine grained homogeneous microstructure is accomplished via solid state sintering of the co-precipitated hydroxides hydrogel of aluminium doped with ZrO₂ (0.2% w/w) at the temperature of 1550 °C. The secondary electron images of fired alumina compacts reveal that *in situ* formed nano-zirconia in minor amount is observed to act as grain growth inhibitor for alumina system and augments the formation zirconia toughened coherent Al₂O₃ ceramics.

Keywords : Pure alumina, zirconia, dopant, co-precipitation, sintering, microstructure.

Introduction

Nowadays, pure alumina has emerged as one of the prime high temperature structural ceramic materials. Pure alumina ceramics exhibits unique combination of enhanced properties such as exceptional mechanical strength, high abrasion resistance, excellent thermal and chemical durability and superior electrical resistivity with low dielectric losses at high frequency. A wide spectrum of pure alumina products finds extensive applications in various fields such as, engine components, refractory linings in cement, iron and steel making furnaces, catalyst carrier, grinding media, electrical insulators, electronics, hip prosthesis, bioceramics and ceramic membranes.

The solid state sintering of high purity micro fine α -Al₂O₃ based items in absence of liquid phase is a very difficult task which is largely governed by lattice diffusion and grain boundary diffusion mechanism. Hence, technological processing of high purity alumina products necessitates a very high temperature (> 1600 °C) for its effective densification. Sintering of alumina ceramics at relatively low temperature to develop dense body with

uniform microstructure and sufficient mechanical properties which is the utmost target of technological investigation requires a prospective sintering aid to create either solid solution or formation of secondary phase or both, by the various diffusion mechanisms.

In fact, the generation of superior alumina ceramics of desired characteristics not only demands proper selection of high purity alumina including its crystal form, state of fineness of the particles, impurities level at the grain boundary but also choice of prospective sintering aid in order to control the densification, phase transformation and micro structural features of alumina compacts at a lower sintering temperature.

The literature review on sintering of alumina reveals that the control of abnormal grain growth is the key step for making non-porous dense alumina ceramics.

Zirconia is recognized as a potential additive which can induce both strength and toughness in ceramic materials. In zirconia toughened alumina, toughening has been attributed to stress induced transformation or microcrack nucleation¹.

The stabilization of zirconia in the tetragonal form is essential for stress induced transformation toughening, while dispersion of uniform zirconia particle is equally important for optimizing microcrack induced toughening². Coble highlighted that small addition of MgO (0.25%) to alumina results in densification of alumina close to its theoretical density³.

Further works of Ayadi and Lukin demonstrated that MgO addition improves the sinterability while the addition of partially stabilized zirconia increases the ultimate strength of alumina ceramics in 3 point bending to 450 MPa⁴. But there are certain uncertainties about the exact role of MgO on the sintering of alumina, though it is widely agreed that the function of MgO is to prevent the pore boundary separation and inhibit the abnormal grain growth.

The effect of minor *in situ* Cr₂O₃ as dopant to pure alpha alumina compacts exhibits profound mineralizing action on the sintering of pure alpha alumina ceramics and results in excellent thermomechanical properties and coherent body during sintering at 1550 °C⁵.

Investigation on the sintering of alumina doped with TiO₂ showed that there is no indication of the presence of solid solution upto 1.0–2.5 mole% TiO₂ in Al₂O₃ when sintered in air. The densification is due to the enhanced grain growth along the grain boundaries. Another study revealed that titanium ions enters Al₂O₃ lattice substitutionally, as Ti⁴⁺ addition increases the concentration of Al³⁺ ion vacancies. Based on the argument, it is believed that Ti⁴⁺ enhances the Al³⁺ ion diffusion by an anion vacancy mechanism. The sintering rate of alumina gradually increases when titania is added upto a certain percent, beyond which the rate levels off or decreases due to the formation of a second phase which inhibits the densification⁶.

The effect of MnO₂ on sintering of alumina is very interesting. The addition of only 0.025% is found to accelerate both sintering rate and grain growth but addition beyond this percentage decreases the sintering rate probably due to the formation of a second phase⁷.

Northal and Messing demonstrated that the seeding of nanocrystalline transition alumina powder appears to be a viable option for producing high quality alumina based ceramics⁸.

The effect of *in situ* ZnAl₂O₄ or MgCr₂O₄ spinel precursor from the respective co-precipitated hydrogels on the densification behavior of pure alumina system revealed that *in situ* formed respective spinel precursor of 0.2% (w/w) only has profound mineralizing action on sinterability of pure alpha alumina compacts by lowering the sintering temperature as below as 1550 °C resulting in dense microstructure of alumina body where ZnAl₂O₄ spinel precursor is observed to act as grain growth inhibitor and MgCr₂O₄ as normal grain growth accelerator for pure alumina system^{9,10}.

Thus, there is immense scope of work on the solid state sintering behavior of pure alumina bodies by controlled incorporation of some reactive oxide precursor as dopant.

Although several synthetic methods, such as, co-precipitation, sol-gel, spray pyrolysis, microwave assisted combustion and hydrothermal routes are widely used to synthesize ultrafine monosize multi-component precursor, the co-precipitation route is preferentially followed to obtain well homogenized, highly reactive bimetallic precursors with good sintering ability at a relatively low temperature of firing.

Considering all the aspects, the investigation has been attempted to prepare mixed hydroxides hydrogel of aluminium and zirconium through sol-gel route with controlled addition of zirconia up to 0.3% (w/w) only followed by the role of *in situ* formed nano zirconia on the densification behavior of pure alumina host matrix in the temperature range from 1400–1550 °C.

Experimental

Analytical reagent grade aluminium isopropoxide (Loba Chem, India), zirconium oxychloride (Loba Chem, India) and isopropanol (Merck) were chosen as starting materials. Nitric acid (Merck) and deionised water were used as peptizing agent and reaction medium for preparation of mixed hydroxides hydrogel respectively.

The synthesis of co-precipitated hydroxides hydrogel of zirconium and aluminium were carried out by interacting requisite proportion of respective 0.2 M salts solution dissolved in 1 : 1 isopropanol-water medium and raising the pH to 3.5–4.0 by drop wise addition of 1 : 1 nitric acid followed by refluxing at 80 °C for 48 h. The dos-

ages of zirconia to the alumina precursor were purposefully restricted to small proportion from 0.1–0.3% (w/w) only. Thus, batch composition data with varying proportions of zirconia as doping agent were given in the Table 1.

Table 1. The batch composition of the sample (% w/w)

Batch	Al ₂ O ₃	ZrO ₂
I	100.00	0.0
II	99.9	0.1
III	99.8	0.2
IV	99.7	0.3

Similarly, the synthesis of aluminium hydroxide gel from aluminium isopropoxide was accomplished following same procedure as mentioned above. The formed double hydroxides hydrogel of Al-Zr system as well as formed aluminium hydroxide gel was aged for 48 h, filtered through Whatmann-41 filter paper under suction, washed with hot water for five times in order to remove dissolved electrolytes. Next, the gels were dried under vacuum at 80 °C and pulverized. The major portion of pulverized mass was calcined at 500 °C in a muffle furnace for 6 h, cooled and stored in an incubator. The dried mixed precursors were characterized by loose bulk density, specific surface area, FTIR, DTA and XRD studies.

The FTIR spectral analyses of dried zirconia-alumina gel precursors were recorded by Perkin-Elmer 783, UK, spectrometer in KBr phase in the spectral range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹.

Differential thermal analyses of the samples were performed in Shimadzu DT-40 analyzer, Japan at the heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹.

The respective batch mix according to Table 1 was dry mixed with 80% (w/w) calcined and 20% (w/w) dried gel powders intimately in an electrical mixer separately. The gel water present in uncalcined precursor acted as the binder. The batch mixes were then uniaxially pressed into cylindrical pellets at the pressure of 800 kg/cm² in a hydraulic press. Finally, all the samples were bone dried at 110 °C and subjected to firing in an electrically operated programmable muffle furnace at different temperatures from 1400–1550 °C for 2 h.

The degree of densification of the fired samples were determined by measuring different physical properties like

linear shrinkage on firing, apparent porosity, bulk density and cold crushing strength following standard methods. The identification of crystalline phase in fired compacts was performed by powder XRD studies in a Philips automatic X-ray diffractometer (XPRT PRO PW-3071) using Ni filtered Cu-K_α radiation of 1.5405 Å at a scanning speed 2°/min. Microstructural features of freshly fracture surfaces of sintered samples at different temperatures were studied by scanning electron microscopy (QUANTA 200, FEI make, Holland).

The schematic diagram for the preparation of the co-precipitated double hydroxides gel of Al and Zr was shown in the Fig. 1.

Results and discussion

The sintering behavior of host Al₂O₃ matrix in presence of minor co-precipitated zirconia precursor from 0.1–0.3% (w/w) only has been investigated to ascertain the solid solubility limit of ZrO₂. The physico-chemical properties of synthesized Al₂O₃-ZrO₂ precursor are shown in the Table 2. The combined alumina-zirconia precursor powder prepared through co-precipitation route manipulates a homogeneous mixing of ingredients in the atomic scale and allows intimate interaction between the alumina and zirconia precursor. However, aging for 48 h after co-precipitation results in changes of physical and chemical properties of the mixed hydroxides precursor by dissolution and re-crystallization mechanism. The opaque appearance of prepared double hydroxides gel is related to the finer particle size distribution and random orientation of the finer particles. The surface area value of double hydroxides gel is significantly high indicating the fine subdivision of the particles.

The FTIR absorption spectra of synthesized double hydroxides precursors presented in the Fig. 2. The intense IR absorption band at around 479 cm⁻¹ is related to Al-O stretching vibration indicative of the presence of higher covalent character of Al-OH bond in the molecule, while at 1075 cm⁻¹ is associated with the -OH stretching vibration of boehmite. The absorption band in and around 2400 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the characteristic absorption of pseudo boehmite. The IR spectra of zirconia doped alumina gel shows a broad absorption band around 3434 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of bound -OH groups in the molecules. At around 1385 cm⁻¹, the absorption peak

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram for the preparation of the co-precipitated hydroxides gel of aluminium and zirconium.

Table 2. The physico-chemical properties of the co-precipitated ZrO_2 - Al_2O_3 gel precursor

Texture	Soft, fluffy, off white
Solid content (wt%)	40.2
Loss on ignition (wt%)	59.8
Loose bulk density (g/cc)	0.38
DTA peak temperatures (°C)	170, 450 (endo)
Specific surface area (m^2/g)	318
FTIR spectra (cm^{-1})	3422, 1636, 1385, 1075, 479

may be due to presence of Al=O bond. With increase in zirconia content, the absorption in this frequency gradually decreases and reaches lowest with the mixed gel containing 0.2% (w/w) zirconia. But with further increase of ZrO_2 content to 0.3% (w/w), absorption in this frequency increases again. Thus, the occurrence of optimal absorption with respect to zirconia content is being observed corresponding to the formation of maximum Al-O-Zr linkage. At about 1075 cm^{-1} , presence of absorption peak

may be due to coupling of stretching and bending vibration of the -OH group ($\nu_{OH_{str}} + \nu_{OH_{bend}}$). The strong absorption bands at 760 , 630 , 500 cm^{-1} are assigned to the Al-O stretching vibration and at 1143 cm^{-1} is associated with the O-H stretching vibration of boehmite¹¹. The absorption band at about 2400 cm^{-1} is attributed to the characteristic absorption peak of pseudo boehmite¹².

DT-TGA analysis of the sample indicates the presence of respective hydroxide: the first endothermic peak at 170 °C corresponds to the presence of zirconia hydroxide while 2nd endotherm at 450 °C accounts for transformation of pseudo boehmite to intermediate alumina phase. The active mixed oxides powder is likely to be generated *in situ* upon heat treatment at around 500 °C .

XRD pattern of co-precipitated Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 precursor powders shows the presence of pseudo boehmite and bayerite as crystalline phases. Microfine zirconia powder having structural similarity and active sites is likely to

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (A) uncalcined alumina precursor, (B) uncalcined co-precipitated alumina precursor doped with 0.1% (w/w) ZrO₂, (C) uncalcined co-precipitated alumina precursor doped with 0.2% (w/w) ZrO₂, (D) uncalcined co-precipitated alumina precursor doped with 0.3% (w/w) ZrO₂.

behave as prospective sintering aid for densification and phase transformation of alumina system. At the same time, active zirconia precursor undergoes transformation toughening reaction to tetragonal zirconia or cubic zirconia phase during heat treatment at high temperature above 1000 °C, thereby, promoting formation of zirconia toughened dense alumina ceramics. Also, there is least possibility of the formation of glassy phase in case of synthesized zirconia-alumina system during sintering. The addition of zirconia has been kept restricted purposefully up to 0.3% (w/w) only so that zirconia atoms can just occupy the interstitial and vacant sites of the alumina lattice. The variation of firing shrinkage against ZrO₂ content at different firing temperatures is graphically represented in Fig. 3.

It is evident from the Fig. 3 that with the increase in firing temperature, the firing shrinkage increases progressively up to highest temperature of firing (1550 °C)

for all the batches due to enhanced material interaction and material transport by diffusion with consequent elimination of porosity. It may be related to the higher thermal activation rate at higher temperatures. In all the cases, the shrinkage values are high, although it does not cause any deformation or cracks in the body. For any given temperature of firing, it is found that firing shrinkage increases steadily with increasing additive content up to 0.2% (w/w) followed by sharp fall at 0.3% (w/w) addition of dopant. The highest shrinkage of 22.4% is observed in the fired compacts with 0.2% (w/w) ZrO₂ loading at 1550 °C. The degree of densification is usually manifested by the magnitude of apparent porosity of the fired compacts. As reaction proceeds with increase of temperature, the open porosity tends to decrease due to growth of crystals leading to closer bonding between the formed crystallites. The changes in apparent porosity of the fired compacts against temperature of firing have been

Fig. 3. Variation of linear shrinkage (%) of the samples fired at different temperature against varying % (w/w) of dopant.

shown in Fig. 4. The effect of ZrO₂ addition on apparent porosity in host alumina matrix during heat treatment from 1400–1550 °C exhibits distinct descending nature in all the samples. The lowest porosity (12.01%) is obtained with the pellets containing 0.2% (w/w) zirconia fired at 1550 °C while dopant free compact shows 22.1% apparent porosity under same condition. However, it is noted that 0.3% (w/w) zirconia containing bodies exhibit

Fig. 4. Variation of apparent porosity (%) of the samples fired at different temperature against varying % (w/w) of dopant.

higher values of porosity at any temperature of firing indicating certain adverse effect of ZrO₂ at this addition on the degree of densification probably out of noncompatible interfacial bonding at the grain boundary. Bulk densities of the sintered product directly correlate the magnitude of densification. The variation of the bulk densities of the fired compacts as a function of additive content and firing temperature is presented in Fig. 5. The highest bulk density (3.84 g/cc) is achieved with com-

Fig. 5. Variation of bulk density of the samples fired at different temperature against varying % (w/w) of dopant.

pacts containing just 0.2% (w/w) zirconia loading at 1550 °C which accounts for 97% of theoretical density of pure α -alumina while dopant free Al₂O₃ compact attains only 94.97% of theoretical density of pure alumina under same condition. It clearly implies that minor reactive ZrO₂ derived from mixed hydroxides gel on the thermal treatment has marked doping action on sintering of Al₂O₃ host matrix as indicated by excellent improvement of bulk density of fired body at 1550 °C. The mechanical strength of the fired compacts is of great importance while considering a ceramic for structural application. The variation of the CCS values against additive content and firing temperature are graphically shown in Fig. 6. From Fig. 6, it is evident that there is a great improvement of the compressive strength of ZrO₂ doped alumina compacts over dopant free compacts with increase in firing temperature from 1400–1550 °C. The highest CCS of 1954 kg/cm² has been achieved with compacts with 0.2% (w/w) zirco-

Fig. 6. Variation of cold crushing strength (kg/cm²) of the samples fired at different temperature against varying % (w/w) of dopant.

nia loading at 1550 °C. However, 0.3 % (w/w) zirconia doped alumina body exhibits a negative impact on strength development of alumina compacts at any temperature of firing probably due to generation of strain in alumina lattice from the excess accumulation of ZrO₂ at the grain boundary. Thermal shock resistance of all ZrO₂ doped alumina compacts fired at 1550 °C measured by air quenching method at 1000 °C exceeds 30 cycles while that with dopant free one is just 20 cycles. The identification of the crystalline phases of the zirconia doped sintered alumina compacts are carried out by X-ray diffraction method (XPERT PRO PW 3071, Diffractometer) using Ni filter Cu-K_α radiation of wavelength 0.15406 nm with operating voltage and current at 40 kV and 40 mA respectively. Each sample was scanned within 2θ values of 10–80° at the scanning rate of 2°/min. Powder XRD patterns of the sintered samples (Fig. 7) reveal that α-Al₂O₃ (corundum) exists as sole crystalline phase as all the peaks completely matched with the standard peaks of α-Al₂O₃. With increase in firing temperature from 1400 to 1550 °C, the formation of well defined α-Al₂O₃ crystal increased progressively as manifested from the higher relative intensity values for different peaks with increase of firing temperature. This trend is observed with increase in amount of additive content as well. But the best

Fig. 7. Powder XRD patterns of pure alumina compacts doped with 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3% (w/w) zirconia fired at 1550 °C.

result was obtained with sintered compacts doped with 0.2% (w/w) zirconia. At the highest temperature of firing, sharp α-Al₂O₃ crystals are formed with 0.2% (w/w) zirconia compared to 0.1 and 0.3% zirconia. This may correspond to the optimum substitution of the Al³⁺ ions by Zr⁴⁺ ions in the alumina matrix corresponding to composition with 0.2% (w/w) zirconia. From the analysis of the interplanar spacing of the sintered compacts, a poor crystallinity in alumina compacts sintered at 1550 °C is observed. Interplanar spacings of the compacts with 0.1 or 0.3% (w/w) zirconia as dopant have been somewhat distorted due to the presence of either deficient or excess zirconia at the grain boundary. But sintered alumina matrix with 0.2% (w/w) zirconia as dopant shows undistorted perfect lattice parameters of alumina crystal which is responsible for imparting better physical and mechanical properties in the sintered product.

The secondary electron images of fractured surfaces of the samples sintered at different temperature up to 1550 °C are taken in a QUANTA 200, FEI make, Holland, with at least 3000X magnification. SEM images of fracture surfaces of sintered alumina samples with or without additive fired at different temperatures from 1450–1550 °C are shown in Figs. 8–13. The comparison of

Fig. 8. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the Al_2O_3 compacts doped with 0.2% (w/w) ZrO_2 fired at 1450 °C.

Fig. 11. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the Al_2O_3 compacts doped with 0.1% (w/w) ZrO_2 fired at 1550 °C.

Fig. 9. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the Al_2O_3 compacts doped with 0.2% (w/w) ZrO_2 fired at 1500 °C.

Fig. 12. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the Al_2O_3 compacts doped with 0.2% (w/w) ZrO_2 fired at 1550 °C.

Fig. 10. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the pure Al_2O_3 compacts fired at 1550 °C.

Fig. 13. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of the Al_2O_3 compacts doped with 0.3% (w/w) ZrO_2 fired at 1550 °C.

microstructure of sintered alumina compacts without additive reveals that the alumina bodies proceed through excessive grain growth with occasional cluster of sealed and open pores with increase of firing temperature as indicated by the Fig. 10. With the increase of additive content, the dense microstructure is achieved via elimination of pores. However, the micrographs of the samples containing 0.2% (w/w) zirconia fired at 1550 °C (Fig. 12) clearly shows that the grains were almost sub-rounded, uniform in size and shape without abnormal growth. They were also uniformly distributed in the matrix. The grain size measurement by intercept method reveals a small size range from 0.5–1.0 μm only while dopant free alumina compacts exhibits such range from 2.0–3.0 μm, thus grain growth inhibiting action of zirconia dopant in alumina matrix during sintering at 1550 °C is established. The pores are also comparatively smaller and evenly distributed through out the matrix.

In the compacts containing 0.3% (w/w) zirconia (Fig. 13), fine zirconia particles are accumulated in the grain boundary of large faceted α-Al₂O₃ crystals which may be responsible for the drastic deterioration of their strength and other physical properties. In the compacts containing up to 0.2% (w/w) zirconia, Al₂O₃ forms solid solution with ZrO₂ in α-Al₂O₃ lattice as Zr⁴⁺ ions replacing Al³⁺ ions are likely to occupy vacant or interstitial sites of α-Al₂O₃. Zr⁴⁺ ions (1.58 Å) with larger cationic size than Al³⁺ ions (1.02 Å) hinders ionic mobility at the grain boundary, thus acting as grain growth inhibitor for alumina system. The optimum content of 0.2% (w/w) ZrO₂ appears to be its solid solubility limit in the Al₂O₃ matrix.

The sintering action of reactive ZrO₂ at about 0.2% (w/w) only on alumina system may be explained in the way that Zr⁴⁺ ions of the mixed oxides precursor can either occupy vacant sites or isomorphously substitute lower valent Al³⁺ cations in rhombohedral Al₂O₃ lattice thereby creating anion vacancies, which appear to be the driving force for its densification.

Conclusions :

From the densification study of mixed alumina-zirconia precursor, the following conclusions may be drawn :

- (i) *In situ* formed nano zirconia behaves as a potential sintering aid for densification of pure alumina compacts. The low percentage of nano fine ZrO₂ in alumina matrix acts as a grain growth inhibitor in pure alumina ceramics.
- (ii) The effect of minor addition of nano zirconia leads to the formation of dense, well crystalline coherent alumina body during firing at 1550 °C.
- (iii) Sol-gel derived Al₂O₃-ZrO₂ precursor powder containing 0.2% (w/w) ZrO₂ only can be sintered to the extent of 97% of its theoretical density with the remarkable compressive strength at 1550 °C.
- (iv) There is a significant improvement in the thermo mechanical properties of the sintered Al₂O₃ compact containing up to 0.2% (w/w) zirconia, beyond which the mechanical properties drastically deteriorated due to the presence of some free zirconia at the grain boundary of the α-Al₂O₃ crystals causing the entire matrix under strained condition.
- (v) No zirconia bearing phase has been detected from the XRD pattern of minor dopant added sintered alumina compacts indicating complete solid solubility of ZrO₂ in alumina matrix.
- (vi) The secondary electron micrographs of fracture surfaces clearly highlight the uniform dispersion of microfine tetragonal zirconia in the alumina matrix leading to the development of ZrO₂ toughened Al₂O₃ body.

Acknowledgement

One of the author(s) B. K. Sanfui is thankful to CSIR, Government of India, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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